

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in Germany

Country report

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January 2026

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union under Grant Number 101094373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive Summary

Drawing on nationally representative data from February 2025 (N=1,008), this report presents analyses from the I-CLAIM survey on the public perceptions of irregular migration in Germany to showcase the German public's knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants in employment settings.

Evidence from the survey shows widespread overestimation of irregular migration: 85% of participants placed the share of irregular migrants above the likely estimated range in the country (8.3–9.6% of the foreign-born population). This overestimation was most pronounced among older adults and conservative voters, while younger respondents and Greens voters were more accurate or underestimated slightly.

Participants were likely to link irregular status to scenarios reflecting prevailing and current political and media narratives, such as unauthorised border crossings and asylum procedures. Routes more central to producing irregularity, such as visa expiry, employment-linked residence loss, or bureaucratic delays, were not as often identified as important.

With regard to employment, participants associated irregular migration to the sectors of construction, cleaning, catering and hospitality, healthcare, and agriculture. The survey also measured social distance, revealing that acceptance of irregular migrants was highest in public or commercial contexts (e.g. shops or workplaces) and lowest in private ones (e.g. home or family care). Differences across political affiliation were pronounced: voters of CDU and other parties (including AfD) displayed the greatest social distance, while Green voters expressed the least.

When asked about (hypothetical) hiring scenarios, preferences were expressed for national origin, length of residence, personal recommendations, and location of family in Germany. Regarding national origin: candidates from Ukraine were favoured over candidates from Turkey and Syria.

Perceptions of integration were similarly structured around visible markers of belonging and social integration. German language fluency and having friends or family in Germany were the strongest positive predictors of perceived integration, while having one's family or friends abroad was associated with lower integration scores. Respondents generally valued practical indicators of settlement and participation over legal status alone.

Findings show that German perceptions of irregular migration are shaped by political and media framings that emphasise border control and asylum, but also fragmented and inconsistent. Attitudes are not wholly hostile; they mix apprehension with practical considerations and display openness to integration through language and social ties.

These findings underscore the importance of addressing both misperceptions and the broader narrative environment that shapes how irregular migration is discussed in Germany. While overestimation and anxiety remain widespread, the survey reveals potential spaces for more balanced discourse – centred on work, contribution, and everyday coexistence rather than fear and control. This research illustrates how public perceptions of irregular migration in Germany are structured less by empirical knowledge than by dominant political and media narratives, while still allowing space for pragmatic and conditional acceptance in everyday contexts.

1. Introduction

This report presents main findings from an online survey from the Horizon Europe-funded project “Improving the living and labour conditions of irregularised migrant households in Europe” (I-CLAIM) project, which was conducted in Germany in February 2025. The aim of the survey is to use various instruments, including survey experiments, to improve understandings of the public perceptions of irregular migration, a situation in which foreign nationals in a given country do not hold legal residence, which is limited, especially within the context of work and employment. In line with the evidence provided in the I-CLAIM UK report (Lessard-Phillips and Sigona, 2025), this report presents findings from a harmonised analysis of the survey in Germany.

In this report, we build on earlier research (Rheindorf, Vollmer & Liebsch 2024) conducted within the I-CLAIM project, that examined narrative constructions of irregularity across media, politics, and civil society in Germany. In this earlier research, the way in which discourse linked to irregular migration is framed and influenced by various stakeholders within these domains was investigated, paying close attention to the interplay of representations of irregular migration and irregular migrants linked to employment, gender, race, and family.

That work revealed a marked disconnect between irregular border crossing-focused narratives (“illegale Einwanderung”) and the complex reality of the phenomenon shaped by Germany’s complex interaction of migration law, asylum procedures, and labour market regulation. We refer to this as the legal and policy infrastructures of irregularity (Rheindorf & Vollmer 2025a, 2025b). These earlier findings directly informed the design of the I-CLAIM survey in Germany. Rather than treating public attitudes as detached opinions, the survey instruments were constructed to test how dominant political and media framings of irregular migration – particularly those centred on border crossings, asylum, and legality – shape public knowledge, misperceptions, and evaluative judgements. In this sense, the survey functions not only as a descriptive tool, but also as a means of empirically probing the narrative environment identified in prior discourse-analytic research.

The survey draws on these results as well as the concept ‘irregularity assemblage’ (Sigona et al. 2021; Piemontese and Sigona 2024), which positions irregularity dynamically in relation to the state and is co-constructed by regulatory frameworks (Gonzalez et al., 2019). On this basis, the survey investigates who is perceived as ‘irregular’, what meanings are attached to the term, and how these perceptions shape public responses in Germany.

Rather than outline all results linked to the survey, in this report we first present information about the survey and participants before focusing on answering two main questions:

- 1) What does the German public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants?
- 2) What are public attitudes in Germany toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?

2. About the Survey

2.1. Development and methodology

The I-CLAIM survey was primarily designed to capture perceptions and attitudes toward irregular migration among the German public but also to collect information about participants' characteristics as well as their general views on immigration.

Co-developed with the I-CLAIM consortium, conducted online, and administered by YouGov, the survey included 25 questions across six main sections, combining traditional items with survey experiments,¹ and covering questions related to knowledge of irregular migration, attitudes toward irregular migrants in work contexts, and socio-demographic characteristics (including some provided by YouGov as part of questions included in their panels – see Abraham (2025) for details). A testing and piloting phase was also conducted prior to fieldwork. Details of the main topics covered by the survey can be found in the Appendix (Table A.1).

2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork

The target population for the survey was the German adult population. The sample was drawn from YouGov's panel of registered users through their "targeted quota sampling" method (see Abraham, 2025) and weights were provided for the sample to reflect Germany's demographic composition in terms of age, gender and education; region and vote at the 2021 election; location and political interest.

Fieldwork activities took place between 6th and 17th February 2025 and the sample comprised a total of 1,008 respondents.

2.3. Data Analysis

All analyses were conducted in Stata using appropriate methods for each research question and applying sampling weights. For categorical variables, we reported weighted frequency distributions and used chi-squared tests and difference in proportion tests to assess associations and differences, ensuring that no percentages are based on fewer than five cases. For continuous variables, means and standard deviations were calculated, with t-tests applied where relevant to compare group differences. Experimental data were analysed using Average Marginal Component Effects (AMCE) (Hainmueller et al., 2014) to estimate selection probabilities across attributes and Marginal Means (MMs) (Leeper et al., 2019) to capture subgroup preferences. Cases with missing data were excluded from specific analyses, resulting in variable sample sizes across questions.

Survey respondents' main characteristics

We begin with a short overview of the main characteristics of German respondents to the I-CLAIM survey. These characteristics serve two purposes: they outline the composition of survey respondents and identify key groups for comparison in terms of knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration.

¹ Survey experiments gauge public opinion by systematically varying question wording or attributes to identify how specific factors influence responses. This approach has become increasingly common in migration research (Sobolewska & Lessard-Phillips, 2024).

Supporting tables can be found in the appendix (Tables A.2–A.4), with Table A.2 presenting the core demographic details. The mean age of the sample (not shown) was just over 50 years, with 31.5% aged 18–39, 43.3% aged 40–64, and 25.2% aged 65 and over. There were 50.9% female respondents and 49.1% male respondents. A mere 2.8% of respondents reported as being a member of a minority ethnic group. Most respondents were either married or partnered (59.2%) and mostly lived in suburban or rural areas (60.5%). The geographical distribution of respondents was predominantly West (83.6%) over East (16.4%).

Table A.3 presents more socio-demographic characteristics. In terms of education, 35.4% of the German respondents reported having low levels of education, 31.3% having medium levels of education (Abitur-level or equivalent, up to university diploma), and 33.2% having high levels of education (first degree or higher). Just over 55% of respondents were in work (either full-time or part-time). Among those providing a figure, 57.4% of respondents were deemed as being in households with a low level of income (<€2500 pm), 41.4% in middle-income households (€2500–€9,999 pm), and 1.2% in higher income households (€10,000 & over pm). In terms of vote choice in the 2021 election, 20.4% of respondents who provided an answer to the question indicated having voted for SPD, 19.1% for CDU/CSU, 11.8% for Greens, 8.3% for AfD and 9.1% for FDP. In the sample, 20.4% indicated that they did not/could not vote or did not know how they voted.

Table A.4 explores respondents links with, and experiences of, migration. A total of 3.4% of respondents indicated being born outside of Germany, with just under 17% having some type of immigrant parentage (again, amongst those providing an answer). Most respondents (91.8%) reported having no migration experience themselves, and 34.6% of respondents indicated having some friends with an immigration background.

In this report, we use some of the characteristics presented above to look at group differences by gender (male/female), age (18–39; 40–64; 65+), and political affiliation based on the party voted for in the last national election (SPD, CDU/CSU, Greens, other parties, and non-voters/don't know).

2.3.1. *Views toward immigration*

Going beyond demographic characteristics, we also briefly cover respondents' general attitudes regarding immigration and immigrants. These are especially relevant if we think of their linkages to perceptions of irregular migration.

The survey started by asking respondents about whether immigration featured as a concern for Germany as well as themselves. Just over 63% of respondents indicated that immigration was a concern for the country, whereas 57.5% identified it as a personal concern. This emphasises the continued salience of immigration as a high-priority political issue in German public opinion, a pattern consistently observed in national and European opinion polling (ARD 2025; European Commission 2025). The gap between perceived national concern and personal concern mirrors a broader pattern in German opinion research, where migration is often framed as a collective or societal problem rather than an immediate personal one (ARD 2025).

We also asked respondents to share their views on migration's costs and benefits by rating two aspects: (1) immigrants' contribution in terms of taxes and services (Figure 1), and (2) immigrants' contribution toward Germany's cultural life (Figure 2). These questions follow ones asked in the European Social Survey (Heath et al., 2016). Responses were given on a 0–10 scale, with 0 meaning a negative contribution and 10 a positive

contribution. For this report, we grouped scores as Negative (0–4), Neutral (5), and Positive (6–10), and explored differences across gender, age, and vote choice.

Figure 1 shows that 53.6% of the respondents had a negative view of immigrants' contribution in terms of tax and services, and thought that immigrants take out more than they put in; 22.6% indicated that immigrants put in more than they take out (positive view). We found no significant differences between men and women and across age groups.

There were significant differences by party affiliation: those voting SPD held less negative views than those voting CDU, other parties or those who did not vote, but more than those voting Greens, Those voting Greens held less negative views than all other groups. We found no voting behaviour-related differences in neutral view on migration.

Regarding positive views, we found a similar picture as for negative views, where people voting Greens held more positive views on migration than all other groups. Those voting SPD held more positive views than those voting CDU, those voting for other parties and those without reported voting behaviour.

Figure 1 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: immigrant take out/put in more (taxes and services). Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=931.

Regarding views toward immigrants' contribution to Germany culture, 45.5% of respondents had a more negative outlook (immigrants undermine German culture), whereas 39.5% had a more positive outlook (immigrants enrich German culture), and 15% taking a neutral view. Despite male respondents having a slightly more positive outlook (40.3%) than women (38.7%), this was not significant. Middle-aged respondents, however, were more negative (48.2%) and less positive (34.8%) than older respondents (40.1%/42.8%). Respondents who voted for other parties (including AfD) exhibited the most negative outlook (56%), followed by respondents without reported voting behaviour (55.8%) and those who voted for the CDU (47%). Respondents who voted Greens had the most positive outlook (70.2%).

Figure 2 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: Cultural life undermined/enriched by immigrants. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=972.

These general attitudes toward immigration provide an important baseline against which perceptions of irregular migration should be read; however, as the following sections show, views on irregularity are structured by distinct assumptions and narratives that cannot be reduced to general pro- or anti-immigration positions.

3. Main Results

Now that we have a better understanding of who the survey respondents were and their views on immigration, in this section we focus on views toward irregular migration and irregular migrants. We do so by showcasing answers (overall and by main group) to the report's focal questions:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants? [knowledge section]
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work? [attitudes section]

3.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants

This section examines respondents' knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants. It begins with perceptions of scale and concern, followed by scenarios that may lead to irregularity. The discussion then shifts to work-related aspects, including sectors where irregular migrants are thought to be employed and measures of social distance toward them.

3.1.1. *Scale and level of concern*

Reliable information on the number of irregular migrants in Germany is scarce; recent estimates place the share of irregular migrants among the foreign-born population at 8.3–9.6% (MIRREM, 2024). To assess respondents' knowledge and potential knowledge gaps, we asked them to estimate the proportion of irregular migrants among all foreign-born residents. Responses were compared with published benchmarks and grouped into four categories: below the estimated range (<8%), on/around the range (8–10%), up to 10% above the estimated range (11–21%), and more than 10% above (22%+). Figure 3 presents these results.

Figure 3 shows that 85% of respondents overestimated the share of irregular migrants in the country (64.2% by over 10%); 9.5% underestimated this share and 5.4% of respondents estimated within the range. We found a significant difference between genders: women were lower in underestimating and higher in overestimating by more than 10%. We also note an age difference: younger and middle-age respondents underestimated more than older respondents (65+); younger respondents had lower rates of 'accurate' estimates, and, finally, older respondents overestimated the share of irregular migrants by the largest margin by far. There is also significant variation by party affiliation: respondents who voted Greens had a higher percentage of underestimation compared to other groups, and they also had higher percentage of accurate estimation than CDU voters. Regarding overestimation by less than 10%, voters of the SPD did so more often than voters of the CDU. And overestimation by more than 10% is most common in non-voters and voters of other parties (including AfD), followed by voters of the CDU, SPD and Greens (although not all differences were significant).

Respondents' evaluation of the share of irregular migrants among the foreign-born population

Figure 3 Perception of the scale of irregular migration in Germany against estimates. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=890. No vote below and on/around estimate categories merged due to small cells.

We also asked respondents whether irregular migration was a concern for Germany, on a 0 (not a concern) to 10 (a great concern) scale and Figure 4 shows the percentage of respondents who indicated irregular migration being a concern (score over 5): 79.8% of respondents indicated that it was. Despite women seeing migration as a concern more frequently (82.9%) than men (77.7%), this was not deemed significant. We also found significant differences across age groups: people aged 18-39 see irregular migration as less as a concern than both older age group; and middle-aged people see it as less of a concern than 65+; in other words, the older, the more concerned the respondents were about irregular migration. In terms of voting behaviour, respondents voting Greens were least frequently concerned (56.1%); among the most concerned were CDU (83.7%), others (including AfD, 86%) and finally the no-vote group (86.6%).

Figure 4 Irregular Migration as concern for Germany. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=981.

The scale of overestimation observed here suggests that public concern about irregular migration is not driven primarily by empirical knowledge of its prevalence, but by broader symbolic and political associations attached to the category of ‘irregular migration’. Overestimation is therefore best understood as a narrative effect, reflecting the prominence of irregularity in political debate and media coverage rather than lived exposure or statistical reality.

3.1.2. *Becoming ‘irregular’: testing scenarios*

Beyond questions on the size of the irregular migrant population and its policy relevance, we also examined respondents’ knowledge about how irregularity occurs. To look into this, one of the questions in the survey presented different scenarios that could lead to irregular status and asked respondents how often they believed these situations could result in irregularity. Exploring public perceptions of these scenarios is particularly relevant given I-CLAIM’s work on narratives of irregularisation (Rheindorf and Vollmer 2025a, 2025b), which shows that political and media discourse overwhelmingly focuses on unauthorised crossings and asylum seekers, often portraying them negatively, while ignoring other drivers of irregularity.

The scenarios were drawn from our earlier research on Germany’s legal and policy architecture (and in the other I-CLAIM countries) and on political and media narratives, which often misalign with the actual processes that produce irregularity. The scenarios shown to respondents included: (1) having an expired student visa; (2) crossing a border without documentation; (3) waiting for an asylum decision; (4) being born in Germany to parents without legal residence; (5) being hired through a recruitment company; and (6) an EU national between employment contracts.

Table 1 summarises responses for each scenario, showing the share of participants who considered it likely ('most of the time' or 'always'), unlikely ('never' or 'sometimes'), or were uncertain (who answered 'don't know').

Table 1 Scenarios of irregularity. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

		Likelihood of scenario leading to irregularity		Uncertainty regarding scenario (N=1,008)
		Most/All of the time	Never/Sometimes	
Scenarios	Waiting to hear about their asylum claim (N=849)	74.8%	25.2%	16.7%
	Crossing a border without proper documentation (N=843)	65.0%	35.0%	17.5%
	Being born in Germany to parents who do not have legal residence status (N=813)	47.4%	52.6%	20.0%
	Being hired through a recruitment company (N=727)	34.3%	65.7%	28.6%
	Having an expired student visa (N=725)	25.5%	74.5%	28.6%
	Being a UK worker in the EU (N=590)	15.4%	84.6%	41.5%

Levels of uncertainty varied substantially across scenarios, with particularly high uncertainty for employment-related and EU mobility scenarios. This pattern is analytically important: rather than indicating respondent indifference, it points to a lack of stable public narratives around administrative and bureaucratic routes into irregularity. In contrast to border- and asylum-related scenarios, which are heavily politicised and widely discussed, these forms of irregularisation appear less publicly legible.

Among the scenarios presented, waiting for an asylum decision and crossing a border without documentation were most frequently identified as leading to irregular status, reflecting patterns in political and media narratives. This is analytically significant, as asylum seekers awaiting a decision have the legal right to remain in Germany, highlighting the gap between legal frameworks and public perceptions. Furthermore, the UN Refugee Convention clearly states that irregular border entry should not prevent or negatively influence the assessment of a person seeking international protection. We look at these in more detail before looking at more 'administrative' routes to irregularity.

Looking at the results for the scenario based on asylum claim more closely, in terms of differences among respondents, we do not see major differences in how different social groups gauge the importance of waiting for an asylum claim (Figure 5) as a likely scenario leading to irregularity. The choice of this scenario is consistent across groups and shows high linkage with irregularity.

Figure 5 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: waiting to hear about an asylum claim. Source: I-CLAIM survey(2025).

In contrast, views on crossing a border without documentation showed significant differentiation by party affiliation. The 'no vote' group were most certain that this will lead to irregular status (75.3%), followed by voters of 'other' parties (70%), CDU (64%), SPD (62.9%), and significantly less by voters of the Greens (40.7%). There were, however, no other major differences in choosing this scenario, once again showing consistency across groups.

Figure 6 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: crossing a border without documentation. Source: I-CLAIM survey(2025).

Of the scenarios viewed as less probable, the case of being born to parents without legal residence revealed differences linked to gender and political affiliation. The 'no vote/don't know' group were most certain that this will lead to irregular status (57.2%), followed by voters of 'other' parties (50.4%), SPD (43.2%), CDU (42.5%), and Greens (42.2%), but only significantly different with CDU voter. Interestingly, this scenario showed a significant difference in gender, with 53.4% of women and only 41.3% of men certain this would lead to irregularity.

Figure 7 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: children born to parents without legal residence. Source: I-CLAIM survey(2025).

Finally, the scenario of being a worker from the UK in the EU showed little differentiation along voting behaviour, but some regarding age groups. In this instance, respondents from the 65+ group had a higher share of choosing this scenario as likely compared to the middle aged group.

Figure 8 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: UK workers in the EU. Source: I-CLAIM survey(2025).

3.2. Irregular migrant and work: sectors & overall feelings

In line with I-CLAIM’s interest in working conditions, respondents shared their knowledge of irregular migration in terms of work, identifying key sectors where irregular migrants are present and expressing their views on meeting such workers in various settings.

Although 44.7% respondents associated work or employment to legal residence, they still identified the main sectors where irregular migrants are perceived to work. Commonly mentioned sectors for male irregular migrants included construction, transportation, cleaning, and agriculture, while for female irregular migrants they included cleaning, catering and hospitality, childcare and elderly care, and healthcare. These patterns were broadly consistent across all respondent groupings.

Table 2 Main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

	First	Second	Third	Fourth
Male	Construction	Transportation	Cleaning	Agriculture
Female	Cleaning	Catering and hospitality	Child and elderly care	Healthcare

Respondents were also allowed to write in sectors not included in the provided list. Although only a small number chose this option, analysis of the free-text responses revealed additional sectors of relevance, such as drug-related activities, crime, and sex work, the latter particularly noted in relation to female workers.

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of comfort with irregular migrants in various professional settings, as a measure of perceived ‘social distance.’ Specifically, they were asked whether they would mind having an irregular migrant working in their home, workplace, or a shop. Levels of comfort were recorded on a scale from 0 (would not mind at all) to 10 (would mind a great deal). Figure 9 presents the mean social distance scores for the overall sample and by group, with higher scores reflecting greater perceived social distance with irregular migrants in the particular setting.

Figure 9 Social distance indicators. Source: I-CLAIM survey(2025). Baseline Ns=864/856/901

Respondents indicated feeling most uncomfortable with irregular migrants in their homes and least uncomfortable meeting them in shops. There were also variation across respondent groups. Women and younger respondents were generally more accepting than men and older respondents. Political leanings shaped attitudes: non-voters, 'other,' and CDU supporters showed the greatest distance, SPD voters moderate, and Greens the least. While most groups ranked home highest, Greens viewed workplace and shop encounters similarly. This gradient suggests that acceptance of irregular migrants is spatially and socially conditional: tolerance is higher where interaction remains impersonal or economically mediated, and lower where it enters domains associated with intimacy, trust, or care.

3.3. Attitudes

Having examined respondents' knowledge of irregular migration and their perceived social distance toward irregular migrants in different settings, we now turn to more specific attitudes toward irregular migration within the context of work and employment, considering intersections with racialisation and gender. This focus is particularly relevant to I-CLAIM, where public perceptions and attitudes inform the narrative construction and production of irregularity. In the survey, these attitudes were assessed through survey experiments, a generally unobtrusive method for eliciting individual preferences on sensitive topics while minimising bias. In this section, we present findings from two such experiments: one on hiring preferences for irregular migrants and another on evaluations of their level of integration into German society

3.3.1. *Hiring choice*

In the hiring choice experiment, respondents were presented with hypothetical applicants for a caregiving role, a sector frequently identified by respondents as a key area of employment for irregular migrants. Each respondent evaluated two pairs of candidates, one male and one female, who shared certain characteristics but lacked proof of residence in Germany, implying irregular status. Based on the provided information, respondents indicated the likelihood of hiring each candidate and selected one for the position. Candidate attributes varied by country of origin and associated name (see Table A.5 in the Appendix), length of residence in Germany, recommendation status, and family location. Figure 10 illustrates an example of the information shown to respondents.

Figure 11 Results from hiring choice experiment (Average Marginal Effects). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,008.

Figure 11 shows that respondents were most likely to hire applicants from Ukraine compared to those from Turkey or Syria, regardless of gender. The effect was slightly more negative for Syrian applicants, particularly men, though not significantly so. Candidates with a longer duration of residence in Germany and those recommended by a friend were more likely to be hired, with both effects stronger for female applicants; the recommendation effect was non-significant for male applicants. Finally, candidates supporting family members based in Germany were evaluated more positively, though this effect was somewhat smaller for female candidates. These patterns indicate that hiring preferences are structured not only by pragmatic considerations such as residence duration and family location, but also by racialised and geopolitically salient hierarchies of origin, which operate even when legal status is held constant.

The preference for specific attributes across respondent groups is shown through Marginal Means in Figures 12 to 14, indicating how each individual attributes are favoured by groups of respondents. Again, a data point to the right of the dotted line indicates a positive preference, whereas one to the left indicates a negative preference. A data point that crosses the dotted line indicates no preference.

Figure 12 shows that male and female respondents did not differ significantly in their preference regarding origin, length of stay, or family location. However, recommendation status appears to influence male respondents' decisions, but not those of female respondents.

Figure 12 Attribute preference by gender of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,008.

We note some significant differences in preferences in terms of the age groups of respondents (Figure 13). The origin of applicants mattered most for the oldest age group (65+) and least for the youngest age group (18-39), widening the gap between preferences with age. There was little difference between age groups regarding the impact of length of residence, and the question of recommendation by a friend mattered least for the oldest age group. Interestingly, preference for whether the applicant's family was in the country of origin or Germany was significant in the younger age groups (18-39 and 40-64) but did not matter for the 65+ group.

Figure 13 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,008.

There were more differences in attribute preferences by political affiliation (Figure 14). For instance, voters of SPD and ‘other’ parties had a positive preference for Ukrainian applicants and negative preference for the Turkish ones. Voters of the CDU had negative preference for the applicant from Syria. Length of residence had a similar impact on voters of SPD and CDU, but less impact on voters of the Greens and voters of ‘other’ parties. Location of the applicant’s family was preferred by all respondents aside from CDU voters.

Figure 14 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=970.

3.3.2. Perceptions of integration and settlement

To further explore attitudes toward irregular migrants, we examined perceptions of their long-term settlement and integration through another experiment looking at evaluations of integration. This focus is important because, while public discourse often frames irregularity around newly arrived migrants, many irregular migrants have lived in Germany for years, and earlier results have also highlighted the relevance of length of residence. We also concentrated on male irregular migrants, who are frequently portrayed most negatively in popular narratives.

Respondents were asked to evaluate the level of integration of two male profile, one from Morocco and one from Moldova, that included randomly varied characteristics considered influential in shaping integration perceptions (see Table A.6 in the Appendix): reason for migration, language fluency, religiosity, location of family and friends, and marital status. They were asked to rate integration on a scale from 0 (not well integrated at all) to 10 (very well integrated). Figure 15 provides an example of the profiles shown to respondents as well as the question asked.

Figure 16 Results from perceptions of integration experiment, all profiles (Average Marginal Effects). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=951.

Figure 17 Results from perceptions of integration experiment, by origin of profile (Average Marginal Effects). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=951

In terms of group preferences (Figures 18-20), we see some variation in some instance. Preferences between male and female respondents (Figure 18) are generally consistent.

Figure 18 Attribute preference by gender of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=951

In terms of difference across age groups (Figure 19), we tend to see more positive preferences among younger age groups. In detail, the younger age group expressed positive preference for both origins (more positive for the profile from Moldova). The youngest age group also had a positive preference for profiles showing no reason for migration or for education as the reason. Fluency mattered more positively for the youngest age group, whereas preference for lack of fluency was more negative for older respondents. Practicing religion was also positively preferred by the youngest age group. The location of friends and family in Germany was positive for all age groups, but the youngest group had a neutral attitude towards them being in the applicant's country of origin, while this was negative for the older groups – especially for 40-64. Family status was positively evaluated by the youngest, especially being married.

Figure 19 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=951.

There were also preference differences across party affiliation (Figure 20). Green voters held the most positive views overall: they expressed positive preferences for almost all attributes, including reasons for migration. SPD voters also expressed positive preference for profiles with individual from Moldova. Language fluency was linked to positive preferences for all groups, but lack of fluency was negative for all groups except Greens. Similarly, the location of friends and family in Germany was preferred for all groups, and location in the country of origin linked to negative preferences for CDU voters.

Figure 20 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=921.

Taken together, these results show that public evaluations of integration among irregular migrants are anchored less in formal legal criteria than in everyday markers of social participation. Integration is imagined as a relational and practical achievement (speaking German, maintaining local social ties, appearing settled) rather than as a function of status alone.

4. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the I-CLAIM survey, this report shows that public perceptions of irregular migration in Germany reveal a striking tension between alarmist narratives and pragmatic reasoning. While political and media discourse often frames irregularity through the lens of border crossings and asylum, everyday attitudes show a more layered picture – one shaped by misperceptions, generational divides, and conditional acceptance when practical considerations come into play.

A first key finding concerns the scale of misperception. Most respondents (85%) overestimated the share of irregular migrants living in Germany, often by a large margin. This was especially pronounced among older respondents and those identifying with conservative or right-leaning parties, whereas Green voters were the most accurate or underestimated slightly. Such overestimation indicates that public knowledge about irregular migration in Germany remains limited and heavily shaped by dominant political and media framings, in which “illegale Einwanderung” and border crossings serve as the central narrative reference points.

Second, the data show that concern about irregular migration is widespread but unequally distributed. Nearly four in five respondents considered irregular migration a major issue for the country. Levels of concern rose consistently with age and were strongest among CDU and ‘other parties’ (including AfD) voters, as well as respondents without declared party preference. By contrast, younger respondents and Greens voters expressed considerably less anxiety about the topic. These findings mirror broader patterns of political polarisation around migration in Germany, where the issue remains one of the most salient yet divisive topics in public debate.

When asked about pathways into irregularity, respondents primarily associated it with unauthorised border crossings or pending asylum procedures, while fewer recognised more routine or administrative routes, such as the loss of residence through employment changes or expiring permits. This confirms the dominance of border- and asylum-related imagery in German discourse, even though irregularity in Germany often emerges from complex bureaucratic or policy processes rather than overt illegality. High levels of uncertainty regarding administrative routes into irregularity further indicate that public knowledge is fragmented and uneven, reinforcing the dominance of highly politicised narratives over less visible legal and bureaucratic processes.

Attitudes toward irregular migrants as workers were more nuanced. Respondents identified construction, cleaning, catering and hospitality, care, and agriculture as the main sectors in which irregular migrants are employed. While the majority expressed discomfort with irregular migrants working in private spaces such as the home, acceptance was notably higher in public or commercial settings, suggesting a boundary between perceived private and public legitimacy of irregular labour.

The hiring experiment results further underline this pragmatism. Respondents generally preferred candidates from Ukraine, followed by Turkey, while Syrian applicants – particularly men – were least likely to be hired. Length of residence in Germany and having family in the country were strong positive predictors of hireability, especially for female applicants. These preferences show how public evaluations are filtered through both gendered and racialised hierarchies, but also through practical considerations of familiarity, perceived stability, and social integration.

Similarly, the integration experiment revealed that language fluency and having social and family ties in Germany were key determinants of perceived integration. Respondents were less influenced by religiosity or marital status. Overall, attitudes toward integration reflected an understanding of belonging rooted in everyday sociocultural participation – speaking German, having family and friends locally, and appearing settled – rather than strictly legal status.

Taken together, these findings suggest that public perceptions of irregular migration in Germany are shaped by a persistent tension between anxiety and normalisation. On the one hand, high levels of concern and widespread overestimation reflect a politicised and often alarmist narrative environment. On the other hand, when faced with specific, humanised scenarios – such as employment or family presence – respondents demonstrate conditional acceptance and pragmatic reasoning.

For policy and communication, these findings point to three interrelated challenges. First, widespread numerical misperceptions indicate a need for interventions that address exaggerated estimates without reinforcing alarmist frames. Second, the dominance of border- and asylum-centred narratives obscures the administrative and labour-related processes through which irregularity is most commonly produced. Third, the conditional acceptance observed in work and integration scenarios suggests that public debate may be more productively reframed around contribution, social participation, and everyday coexistence rather than legality alone. Ultimately, the survey underscores that irregular migration in Germany, as elsewhere, is not merely a legal status but a social and political category produced through interaction between institutions, public discourse, and individual experience. Understanding how these layers intersect – how irregularity is imagined, judged, and morally ordered by the public – is essential to fostering more balanced and informed discussions about migration, belonging, and social cohesion in Germany. For research and policy alike, this underlines the need to engage not only with attitudes as fixed positions, but with the narrative conditions under which irregular migration becomes intelligible, contested, or normalised in public life.

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Appendices

Table A.1 Overview of the content of the I-CLAIM survey

Section	Description of question
A. Overall concerns	Top issues facing the country today
	Top issues facing you personally
B. Attitudes and experience toward immigration	Close friends as immigrants (split allocation)
	Whether immigrants take more in or out of society
	Whether cultural like undermined or enriched by immigrants
	Views on immigrants and work
C. Perception of irregular migration/migrants	Percentage of irregular migrants in country
	Whether irregular migration is a concern in country
	Work sector for female irregular migrants
	Work sector for male irregular migrants
	Scenarios of irregularity
D. Attitudes toward irregular migration and work/employment	List experiment on policy deservingness for female cleaner
	Conjoint experiment – <i>female care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Conjoint experiment – <i>male care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 1</i>
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 2</i>
	Social distance indicator – <i>3 scenarios</i>
	E. Further demographics
Religiosity	
Member of ethnic minority group	
Has lived outside of country for over 1 year	

Table A.2: Main Demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Age (N=1,008)	Adult (18-39)	31.5%
	Middle Age (40-64)	43.3%
	Older adults (65+)	25.2%
Gender (N=1,008)	Male	49.1%
	Female	50.9%
Ethnic Minority (N=970)	No	97.2%
	Yes	2.8%
Marital Status (N=992)	Married, partnership, living as married, in a relationship	59.2%
	Divorced, widowed, separated	15.0%
	Not in a relationship	25.8%
Location (N=1,008)	Urban	39.5%
	Suburban, rural	60.5%
Region (N=1,008)	West	83.6%
	East	16.4%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.3: Socio-demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Education level (N=1,008)	Low	35.4%
	Medium	31.3%
	High	33.2%
Work status(N=1,008)	Working	55.2%
	Not working	44.8%
Household income (N=858)	Low	57.4%
	Medium	41.4%
	High	1.2%
Party voted for in 2021 (N=1,008)	SPD	20.4%
	CDU/CSU	19.1%
	Bündnis 90/Die Grünen	11.8%
	AfD	8.3%
	FDP	9.1%
	Die Linke	3.9%
	Other party	6.9%
	Did Not Vote/Don't Know/Not eligible	20.4%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.4: Respondents' Links to migration

Characteristic	Categories	%
Country of birth (N=1,008)	Outside of Germany	3.4%
	Germany	96.6%
Immigrant parentage (N=1,001)	None	83.1%
	One parent	6.9%
	Two parents	10.0%
Experience of migration (N=1,000)	No	91.8%
	Yes	8.2%
Has immigrant friends (N=989)	None	65.3%
	Yes, several	9.0%
	Yes, a few	25.6%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.5 Attributes for hiring experiment randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN: FEMALE NAME/MALE NAME Two of three chosen for the female and male candidates.	Turkey: Dilan/Adil Ukraine: Dariia/Ivan Syria: Alaa/Ahmad
LENGTH OF RESIDENCE One of two.	under a year 5 years
RECOMMENDATION STATUS One of two.	<no recommendation> but comes recommended by a friend
LOCATION OF FAMILY One of two.	Country of origin Survey country

Table A.6 Attributes for integration experiments randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN/NAME One for each profile	Morocco: Ahmed Moldova : Andrei
REASON FOR MIGRATION One of four.	<no reason stated> to improve his living standards to get an education to seek protection
SURVEY COUNTRY LANGUAGE FLUENCY One of two.	speaks does not speak
RELIGIOSITY One of two.	He regularly practices his religion. <none stated>
LOCATION OF FRIENDS One of two.	From COUNTRY OF ORIGIN From SURVEY COUNTRY
FAMILY STATUS One of two.	He is single He has a family
LOCATION OF FAMILY If has family One of two.	In COUNTRY OF ORIGIN In SURVEY COUNTRY

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I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe